

Supporting Information

Reducing non-radiative voltage losses by methylation of the donor molecules in organic solar cells

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1. General methods

Figure S1. Previously reported push-pull D- π -A molecules^[1-5].

Microwave assisted reactions are performed in the cavity of a Biotage Initiator+ system in sealed reactors. Flash chromatography is performed with analytical-grade solvents using ALDRICH silica gel (technical grade, pore size 60 Å, 230-400 mesh particle size). Flexible plates ALUGRAM Xtra SIL G UV254 from MACHEREY-NAGEL are used for TLC. Compounds are detected by UV irradiation (BIOBLOCK SCIENTIFIC). NMR spectra are recorded with a BRUKER AVANCE III 300 (¹H, 300 MHz and ¹³C, 75MHz). Chemical shifts are given in ppm relative to TMS and coupling constants J in Hz. IR spectra are recorded on a BRUKER spectrometer VERTEX 70 and UV-vis spectra with a PERKIN ELMER 950 spectrometer. Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization is performed on MALDI-TOF MS BIFLEX III BRUKER DALTONICS spectrometer. High resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) is performed with a JEOL JMS-700 B/E or a JEOL Spiral-TOF JMS3000. Recycling-preparative HPLC purification is performed on a LC-9160NEXT system from the Japan Analytical Industry Co., Ltd. (JAI) equipped with coupled UV-vis 4Ch NEXT and RI-700 II detectors at room temperature through a set of two JAIGEL-2H and 2.5H columns at an elution rate of 10 mL min⁻¹.

2. Synthetic procedures

All reagents and chemicals from commercial sources are used without further purification unless specified. 7-Bromo-2,1,3-benzothiadiazole-4-carboxaldehyde is prepared according to literature^[6]. Tetrakis(triphenylphosphine) palladium (0) (Pd(PPh₃)₄) is prepared from PdCl₂ following the previously reported procedure^[7]. Commercial Pd₂(dba)₃ is purified as described^[8]. Solvents are dried and purified using standard techniques.

4-(methyl(phenyl)amino)phenylboronic acid (**2a**).

n-BuLi (1.6 M in hexanes, 1.05 mL, 1.67 mmol) is added dropwise over a solution of 4-bromo-*N*-methyl-*N*-phenylaniline (**1a**) (399 mg, 1.52 mmol) in anhydrous THF (6 mL) cooled to -78 °C. After additional stirring of 1 h at the same temperature, triisopropyl borate (573 mg, 3.04 mmol) is added at once and the mixture is allowed to warm to room temperature for 4 h. The reaction mixture is finally quenched with a 2 M aqueous solution of HCl (1 mL) and poured into water. After extraction with dichloromethane, the organic phase is dried over MgSO₄ and the solvent evaporated under reduced pressure. The resulting crude is precipitated with pentane and filtrated giving 260 mg of a white powder (75%). **¹H-NMR** (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.05 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.38 (t, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 2H), 7.22 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 7.15 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 1H), 6.94 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 3.40 (s, 3H).

7-(4-(methyl(phenyl)amino)phenyl)benzo[*c*][1,2,5]thiadiazole-4-carbaldehyde (**3a**).

In a long single neck flask, compound **2a** (260 mg, 1.15 mmol), 7-bromobenzo[*c*][1,2,5]thiadiazole-4-carbaldehyde (253 mg, 1.04 mmol), NaHCO₃ (263 mg, 3.12 mmol) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (60 mg, 0.05 mmol) are suspended in a mixture of DMF (8 mL) and H₂O (5 mL). The mixture is irradiated under microwaves in the cavity of a CEM®-Discover machine for 15 min at a pre-selected temperature of 150 °C, using a maximum irradiation power of 150 W. The flask is then cooled to room temperature and dichloromethane is added. The organic phase is extracted, washed with water and brine, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude is purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: dichloromethane) affording 292 mg of a red powder (82%). **¹H-NMR** (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 10.73 (s, 1H), 8.26 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 7.97 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 7.82 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 7.44 – 7.35 (m, 2H), 7.25 (dd, *J* = 8.7 Hz, *J* = 0.9 Hz, 2H), 7.17 (tt, *J* = 7.2 Hz, *J* = 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.03 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 3.42 (s, 3H). **¹³C-NMR** (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 189.1, 154.1, 154.1, 150.4, 148.0, 140.5, 133.4, 130.7, 129.8, 126.6, 125.4, 125.2, 124.9, 124.6, 116.2, 40.4. **IR** (neat): ν = 1684 cm⁻¹ (C=O). **MS** (MALDI-LDI+) *m/z*: 345.1 [M+]. **HRMS** (CI+): calculated for C₂₀H₁₅N₃OS 345.0936, found 345.0935.

2-((7-(4-(methyl(phenyl)amino)phenyl)benzo[*c*][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl)methylene)malononitrile (MPA).

Triethylamine (4 drops) is added to a mixture of aldehyde (**3a**) (225 mg, 0.65 mmol) and malononitrile (65 mg, 0.98 mmol) dissolved in acetonitrile (40 mL). The reaction mixture is stirred for 2 h at room temperature. The solvent is removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid is dissolved in the minimum of CH₂Cl₂ and precipitated with pentane. The precipitate is filtered and washed several times with methanol and then pentane affording 256 mg of a brown-golden powder (99%). **¹H-NMR** (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.83 (s, 1H), 8.79 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 8.03 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 2H), 7.84 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 7.46 – 7.38 (m, 2H), 7.27 (dd, *J* = 7.3 Hz, *J* = 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.21 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 7.00 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 2H). **¹³C-NMR** (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 154.9, 153.0, 152.8, 150.8, 147.6, 140.6, 131.1, 130.9, 129.9, 125.7, 125.6, 125.3, 125.2, 121.1, 115.6, 114.3, 113.5, 81.6, 40.4. **IR** (neat): ν = 2223 cm⁻¹ (C≡N). **UV-Vis** (CH₂Cl₂): λ_{max} (ε) = 551 nm (27000 L·mol⁻¹·cm⁻¹). **MS** (MALDI-LDI+) *m/z*: 393.0 [M+]. **HRMS** (EI+): calculated for C₂₃H₁₅N₅S 393.1042, found 393.1046.

4-bromo-*N*-methyl-*N*-(*p*-tolyl)aniline (**1b**).

A 20 mL-long single neck flask is charged with 4-bromiodobenzene (8.96 g, 31.6 mmol, 4 equiv.), Pd₂(dba)₃ (362 mg, 0.40 mmol, 0.05 equiv.), [1,1'-biphenyl]-2-ylidicyclohexylphosphane (270 mg, 0.77 mmol, 0.10 equiv.) and sodium *tert*-butoxyde (913 mg, 9.5 mmol, 1.2 equiv.). After three freeze-pump-thaw cycles using argon, toluene (20 mL) and *N*,4-dimethylaniline (1 mL, 959 mg, 7.9 mmol, 1 equiv.) are successively added. The suspension is stirred for 30 s and then irradiated under microwaves in the cavity of a CEM®-Discover machine for 15 min at a pre-selected temperature of 150 °C, using a maximum irradiation power of 150 W. The solvent is evaporated *in vacuo* and the residue is dissolved in EtOAc. The resulting solution is filtered through a silica plug ishing thoroughly with ethyl acetate. The solution is concentrated *in vacuo* and the crude is purified by column chromatography on silica gel using a 9:1 mixture of petroleum ether/CH₂Cl₂ as eluent, affording **1b** as a white solid (1.7 g, 78%). **¹H-NMR** (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.28 (d, J = 9.0 Hz, 2H), 7.14 (d, J = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 7.00 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 6.73 (d, J = 9.0 Hz, 2H), 3.25 (s, 3H), 2.33 (s, 3H). **¹³C-NMR** (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 148.6, 146.2, 133.4, 131.9, 130.3, 123.8, 118.8, 111.4, 40.5, 22.8. **MS** (MALDI-LDI+) 275/277 [M+]. **HRMS** (EI+): calculated for C₁₄H₁₄BrN 275.0304, found 275.0309.

(4-(methyl(*p*-tolyl)amino)phenyl)boronic acid (**2b**).

A mixture of compound **1b** (1.20 g, 4.35 mmol), bis(pinacolato)diboron (1.32 g, 5.22 mmol, 1.2 equiv.), Pd(dppf)Cl₂ (106 mg, 0.13 mmol, 0.03 equiv.) and KOAc (1.28 g, 13.04 mmol, 3 equiv.) in anhydrous and degassed THF (20 mL) is stirred at 80 °C overnight. The solvent is removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid is dissolved in EtOAc and the solution is filtered through a silica plug ishing thoroughly with ethyl acetate. After evaporation of EtOAc, the crude is purified by column chromatography on silica gel starting from a 1:1 mixture of petroleum ether/CH₂Cl₂ and finishing with pure CH₂Cl₂ as eluents. Compound **2b** is obtained as white powder (370 mg, 26%). **¹H-NMR** (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.66 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.17 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 7.07 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 6.81 (d, J = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 3.31 (s, 3H), 2.36 (s, 3H), 1.33 (s, 12H). **¹³C-NMR** (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 151.8, 145.9, 136.0, 134.0, 130.3, 125.1, 114.9, 83.4, 40.3, 25.0, 21.0. **MS** (EI+) 323.4 [M+]. **HRMS** (EI+): calculated for C₂₀H₂₆BNO₂ 323.2057, found 323.2059.

7-(4-(methyl(*p*-tolyl)amino)phenyl)benzo[*c*][1,2,5]thiadiazole-4-carbaldehyde (**3b**).

In a long single neck flask, compound **2b** (293 mg, 0.91 mmol), 7-bromobenzo[*c*][1,2,5]thiadiazole-4-carbaldehyde (220 mg, 0.91 mmol), NaHCO₃ (228 mg, 2.72 mmol) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (52 mg, 0.05 mmol) are suspended in a mixture of DMF (8 mL) and H₂O (5 mL). The mixture is irradiated under microwaves in the cavity of a CEM®-Discover machine for 15 min at a pre-selected temperature of 150 °C, using a maximum irradiation power of 150 W. The flask is then cooled to room temperature and dichloromethane is added. The organic phase is extracted, ished with water and brine, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude is purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: dichloromethane) affording 150 mg of a red powder (46%). **¹H-NMR** (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 10.72 (s, 1H), 8.24 (d, J = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.95 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 7.79 (d, J = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.22 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 7.15 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 6.95 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 3.39 (s, 3H), 2.38 (s, 3H). **¹³C-NMR** (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 189.0,

154.2, 154.1, 150.7, 145.4, 140.6, 134.9, 133.2, 130.7, 130.5, 125.8, 125.7, 125.2, 125.0, 115.1, 40.4, 21.1. IR (neat): $\nu = 1682 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=O). MS (EI+) 359.2 [M+]. MS (EI+) 359.2 [M+]. HRMS (EI+): calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$ 359.1092, found 359.1085.

2-((7-(4-(methyl(p-tolyl)amino)phenyl)benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl)methylene)malononitrile (Me-MPA).

Triethylamine (4 drops) is added to a mixture of aldehyde (**3b**) (150 mg, 0.42 mmol) and malononitrile (41 mg, 0.66 mmol) dissolved in acetonitrile (40 mL). The reaction mixture is stirred for 30 min at room temperature. The solvent is removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid is dissolved in the minimum of CH_2Cl_2 and precipitated with pentane. The precipitate is filtered and washed several times with pentane affording 136 mg of a dark-blue powder (80%). ¹H-NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.82 (s, 1H), 8.78 (d, $J = 7.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1H), 8.02 (d, $J = 8.9 \text{ Hz}$, 2H), 7.83 (d, $J = 7.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1H), 7.23 (d, $J = 8.5 \text{ Hz}$, 2H), 7.16 (d, $J = 8.4 \text{ Hz}$, 2H), 6.93 (d, $J = 9.0 \text{ Hz}$, 2H), 3.40 (s, 3H), 2.39 (s, 3H). ¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 154.81, 152.85, 152.75, 150.96, 144.94, 140.64, 135.33, 131.06, 130.83, 130.47, 125.98, 125.01, 124.96, 120.87, 114.68, 114.18, 113.39, 81.29, 40.31, 21.02. IR (neat): $\nu = 2225 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C \equiv N). UV-Vis (CH_2Cl_2): λ_{max} (ϵ) = 559 nm (41000 $\text{L}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$). MS (MALDI- LDI+) 407.0 [M+]. HRMS (EI+): calculated for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_5\text{S}$ 407.1199, found 407.1203.

N-methyl-N-phenylthiophen-2-amine (4a).

2-Dicyclohexylphosphino-2',6'-diisopropoxybiphenyl (RuPhos) (340 mg, 0.72 mmol), sodium *tert*-butoxyde (2.43 g, 25.2 mmol), palladium acetate (40.5 mg, 0.18 mmol) are dissolved in anhydrous and degassed toluene (45 mL). Then, methyl aniline (2.39 mL, 21.6 mmol) and 2-bromothiophene (1.79 mL, 18.3 mmol) are added and the mixture is refluxed for 19 h. The reaction is quenched with brine. After separation of the organic phase, the aqueous phase is extracted with dichloromethane. The combined organic phases are washed with water, dried over MgSO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. The final product is purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: petroleum ether/ethyl acetate 20:1) leading to a yellowish oil (2.5 g, 73%). ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 7.29 – 7.21 (m, 2H), 6.98 – 6.93 (m, 3H), 6.92 – 6.85 (m, 2H), 6.65 (dd, $J = 3.6, 1.4 \text{ Hz}$, 1H), 3.33 (s, 3H). In accordance with literature⁹.

7-(5-(methyl(phenyl)amino)thiophen-2-yl)benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazole-4-carbaldehyde (5a).

n-BuLi (1.6 M in hexanes, 1.60 mL, 2.52 mmol) is added dropwise to a solution of **4a** (400 mg, 2.11 mmol) in anhydrous THF (20 mL) cooled down to -78°C . The mixture is stirred for 1 h at this temperature and then tributyltin chloride (0.75 mL, 2.63 mmol) is added. The reaction mixture is warmed to room temperature and stirred for 16 h. The reaction is quenched with water. After separation of the organic phase, the aqueous phase is extracted with dichloromethane. The combined organic phases are washed with water, dried over MgSO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure.

The intermediate stannane, without further purification, is mixed with 7-bromobenzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazole-4-carbaldehyde (540 mg, 2.22 mmol) and tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0) (122 mg, 0.11 mmol) in degassed toluene (30 mL) and the mixture is stirred under reflux for 16 h. After separation of the organic phase, the aqueous phase is extracted

with toluene. The combined organic phases are washed with water, dried over MgSO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude is purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: petroleum ether/ethyl acetate 8:2) affording a purple solid (650 mg, 88%). **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 10.60 (s, 1H), 8.22 (d, $J = 4.3$ Hz, 1H), 8.11 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 1H), 7.65 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 1H), 7.46 – 7.39 (m, 2H), 7.38 – 7.33 (m, 2H), 7.24 – 7.18 (m, 1H), 6.34 (d, $J = 4.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.51 (s, 3H). **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 188.4, 161.0, 154.1, 152.1, 147.5, 134.1, 133.8, 132.5, 129.8, 125.3, 124.4, 123.4, 123.3, 120.4, 109.3, 42.5. **MS** (MALDI-LDI+) m/z : 351.0 $[\text{M}^+]$. **HRMS** (FAB): m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{OS}_2$: 351.0495, found: 351.0494.

2-((7-(5-(methyl(phenyl)amino)thiophen-2-yl)benzo[*c*][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl)methylene)malononitrile (MTA).

Five drops of triethylamine are added to a mixture of compound **5a** (333 mg, 0.95 mmol) and malononitrile (125.2 mg, 1.90 mmol) in acetonitrile (60 mL). The reaction mixture is stirred for 2 h under air at room temperature and then the solvent is evaporated under vacuum. The resulting product is purified using a recycling size-exclusion preparative HPLC affording a dark blue solid (286 mg, 76%). **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 8.67 (s, 1H), 8.64 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 1H), 8.25 (d, $J = 4.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.58 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.50 – 7.42 (m, 2H), 7.41 – 7.36 (m, 2H), 7.32 – 7.27 (m, 1H), 6.31 (d, $J = 4.5$ Hz, 1H), 3.54 (s, 3H). **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 163.4, 155.1, 151.8, 150.8, 147.0, 134.6, 131.3, 130.0, 126.4, 124.3, 124.1, 120.4, 118.6, 115.1, 114.3, 109.0, 42.8. **IR** (neat): $\nu = 2216$ cm^{-1} ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$). **MS** (MALDI-LDI+) m/z : 399.0 $[\text{M}^+]$. **HRMS** (FAB): m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2$: 399.0607, found: 399.0610.

N-methyl-*N*-(*p*-tolyl)thiophen-2-amine (4b).

2-Dicyclohexylphosphino-2',6'-diisopropoxybiphenyl (RuPhos) (226 mg, 0.48 mmol), sodium *tert*-butoxyde (1.62 g, 16.5 mmol), palladium acetate (27.0 mg, 0.12 mmol) are dissolved in dry and degassed toluene (25 mL). Then, *N*,4-dimethylaniline (1.86 mL, 14.4 mmol) and 2-bromothiophene (1.19 mL, 12.0 mmol) are added and then the mixture is refluxed during 19 h. The reaction is filtered through a silica plug washing thoroughly with ethyl acetate. The solution is concentrated under reduced pressure and the final product is purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: petroleum ether/ethyl acetate 20:1) leading to a yellowish oil (820 mg, 34%). **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 7.11 – 7.04 (m, 2H), 6.93 (m, 2H), 6.88 – 6.81 (m, 2H), 6.52 (dd, $J = 3.2, 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 3.31 (s, 3H), 2.29 (s, 3H). **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 154.8, 147.2, 130.3, 129.7, 125.9, 117.9, 117.7, 115.9, 42.4, 20.7. **MS** (EI+) 203.1 $[\text{M}^+]$. **HRMS** (EI): m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{NS}$: 203.0763, found: 203.0763.

7-(5-(methyl(*p*-tolyl)amino)thiophen-2-yl)benzo[*c*][1,2,5]thiadiazole-4-carbaldehyde (5b).

n-BuLi (2.5 M in hexanes, 0.43 mL, 1.07 mmol) is added dropwise to a solution of **4b** (182 mg, 0.90 mmol) in anhydrous THF (10 mL) cooled down to -78°C . The mixture is stirred for 1 h at this temperature and then tributyltin chloride (0.32 mL, 1.12 mmol) is added. The reaction mixture is warmed to room temperature and stirred for 16 h. The reaction is quenched with water. After separation of the organic phase, the aqueous phase is extracted with dichloromethane. The combined organic phases are washed with water, dried over MgSO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure.

The intermediate stannane, without further purification, is mixed with 7-bromobenzo[*c*][1,2,5]thiadiazole-4-carbaldehyde (230 mg, 0.94 mmol) and tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0) (52 mg, 0.04 mmol) in degassed toluene (25 mL) and the mixture is stirred under reflux for 16 h. The reaction is quenched with water. After separation of the organic phase, the aqueous phase is extracted with toluene. The combined organic phases are washed with water, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. The product is purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: petroleum ether/ethyl acetate 8:2) yielding a purple solid (300 mg, 91%). **¹H NMR** (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) 10.58 (s, 1H), 8.23 (d, *J* = 4.3 Hz, 1H), 8.08 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.60 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.31 – 7.17 (m, 4H), 6.24 (d, *J* = 4.3 Hz, 1H), 3.47 (s, 3H), 2.39 (s, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) 188.2, 161.7, 154.0, 152.0, 144.9, 135.7, 134.1, 133.7, 132.8, 130.3, 124.0, 123.5, 122.9, 119.9, 107.8, 42.5, 21.1. **MS** (MALDI-LDI+) 365 [M+]. **HRMS** (EI): *m/z* calcd for C₁₉H₁₅N₃OS₂: 365.0651, found: 365.0651.

2-((7-(5-(methyl(*p*-tolyl)amino)thiophen-2-yl)benzo[*c*][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl)methylene)malononitrile (Me-MTA).

Three drops of triethylamine are added to a mixture of compound **5b** (190.0 mg, 0.52 mmol) and malononitrile (68.7 mg, 1.04 mmol) in acetonitrile (40 mL). The reaction mixture is stirred for 4 h at room temperature and then the solvent is evaporated under vacuum. The resulting solid is dissolved in CHCl₃, then precipitated with pentane and washed thoroughly with pentane leading to a dark blue solid (155 mg, 72%). **¹H NMR** (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) 8.66 (s, 1H), 8.64 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H), 8.26 (d, *J* = 4.5 Hz, 1H), 7.55 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H), 7.28 – 7.26 (m, 4H), 6.24 (d, *J* = 4.5 Hz, 1H), 3.51 (s, 3H), 2.41 (s, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) 164.1, 155.1, 151.7, 150.8, 144.4, 136.7, 134.8, 134.7, 131.3, 130.6, 124.6, 123.6, 120.1, 118.2, 115.2, 114.4, 108.3, 42.9, 22.8. **IR** (neat): *ν* = 2214 cm⁻¹ (C≡N). **MS** (MALDI-LDI+) 413.2 [M+]. **HRMS** (EI): *m/z* calcd for C₂₂H₁₅N₅S₂: 413.0769, found: 413.0763.

3. NMR spectra

Figure S2. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra of **3a** in CDCl₃ at room temperature.

Figure S3. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra of MPA in CDCl₃ at room temperature.

Figure S4. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra of **1b** in CDCl₃ at room temperature.

Figure S5. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra of **2b** in CDCl₃ at room temperature.

Figure S6. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra of **3b** in CDCl₃ at room temperature.

Figure S7. ^1H NMR (300 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz) spectra of Me-MPA in CDCl_3 at room temperature.

Figure S8. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra of **5a** in CDCl₃ at room temperature.

Figure S9. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra of MTA in CDCl₃ at room temperature.

Figure S10. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra of **4b** in CDCl₃ at room temperature.

Figure S11. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra of **5b** in CDCl₃ at room temperature.

Figure S12. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra of **Me-MTA** in CDCl₃ at room temperature.

4. Mass spectra

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[Mass Spectrum]

Data : PSM37-CI+isobutane001 Date : 15-Feb-2018 18:35

RT : 1.16 min Scan# : (109,127)

Elements : C 24/0, H 49/0, N 3/0, O 1/0, S 1/0

Mass Tolerance : 1000ppm, 1mmu if m/z > 1

Unsaturation (U.S.) : -0.5 - 30.0

	Observed m/z	Int%	Err [ppm / mmu]	U. S.	Composition
1	345.0935	16.68	-0.2 / -0.1	16.0	C20 H15 N3 O S
2	346.1006	100.00	-2.3 / -0.8	15.5	C20 H16 N3 O S

Figure S13. MALDI-TOF (top) and chemical ionization (CI+) high resolution (bottom) mass spectra of **3a**.

Comment 1 FLEXControl generated XMASS data
 Comment 2 (c) 2000 Bruker Daltonics

Bruker Daltonics flexAnalysis

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Figure S14. MALDI-TOF (top) and FAB+ high resolution (bottom) mass spectra of **MPA**.

Comment 1 FLEXControl generated XMASS data
 Comment 2 (c) 2000 Bruker Daltonics

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[Mass Spectrum]
 Data : PSM130-EI004 Date : 11-Sep-2018 15:15
 RT : 2.30 min Scan# : (27,38)
 Elements : C 24/0, H 49/0, 79Br 1/0, 81Br 1/0, N 1/0
 Mass Tolerance : 1000ppm, 1mmu if m/z > 1
 Unsaturation (U.S.) : -0.5 - 30.0

Observed m/z	Int%	Err [ppm / mmu]	U. S. Composition
1 275.0309	100.00	-0.2 / -0.1	8.0 C14 H14 79Br N

Figure S15. MALDI-TOF (top) and electron impact high resolution (bottom) mass spectra of **1b**. Note that the peaks at 374, 332 and 250 come from the dctb (2-[(2E)-3-(4-tert-Butylphenyl)-2-methylprop-2-enylidene]malononitrile) matrix.

Data : PSM132-EI001
Inlet : Direct

Date : 12-Sep-2018 15:57
Ion Mode : EI+

[Mass Spectrum]
Data : PSM132-EI001 Date : 12-Sep-2018 15:57
RT : 2.12 min Scan# : (25,41)
Elements : C 24/0, H 49/0, N 1/0, O 2/0, B 1/0
Mass Tolerance : 1000ppm, 1mmu if m/z > 1
Unsaturation (U.S.) : -0.5 - 20.0

Observed m/z	Int%	Err [ppm / mmu]	U.S. Composition
1 323.2059	100.00	+0.7 / +0.2	9.0 C20 H26 N O2 B

Figure S16. Electron impact (top) and electron impact high resolution (bottom) mass spectra of **2b**.

Data : PSM138002
Inlet : Direct

Date : 03-Oct-2018 17:28
Ion Mode : EI+

[Mass Spectrum]
Data : psm138-FAB+Argon002 Date : 03-Oct-2018 11:43
RT : 2.60 min Scan# : (14,15)
Elements : C 24/0, H 49/0, N 3/0, O 1/0, S 1/0
Mass Tolerance : 1000ppm, 1mmu if m/z > 1
Unsaturation (U.S.): -0.5 - 30.0

Figure S17. Electron impact (top) and FAB+ high resolution (bottom) mass spectra of **3b**.

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[Mass Spectrum]

Data : PSM141-FAB+Argon001 Date : 04-Oct-2018 16:19

RT : 11.80 min Scan# : (60.72)

Elements : C 24/0, H 17/0, N 5/0, S 1/0

Mass Tolerance : 1000ppm, 1mmu if m/z > 1

Unsaturation (U.S.) : -0.5 - 30.0

Observed m/z	Int%	Err [ppm / mmu]	U.S. Composition
407.1203	100.00	-0.4 / -0.2	20.0 C24 H17 N5 S

Figure S18. MALDI-TOF (top) and FAB+ high resolution (bottom) mass spectra of **Me-MPA**.

Bruker Daltonics flexAnalysis

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[Mass Spectrum]

Data : JMA38-FAB+argon001 Date : 28-Feb-2018 11:12
 RT : 6.60 min Scan# : (34,40)
 Elements : C 24/0, H 49/0, N 3/0, O 1/0, S 2/0
 Mass Tolerance : 1000ppm, 1mmu if m/z > 1
 Unsaturation (U.S.) : -0.5 - 20.0

Figure S19. MALDI-TOF (top) and FAB+ high resolution (bottom) mass spectra of 5a.

Bruker Daltonics flexAnalysis

printed: 28/02/2018 17:30:12

[Mass Spectrum]
Data : JMA42-FAB+argon002 Date : 02-Mar-2018 11:03
RT : 13.00 min Scan# : (66,73)
Elements : C 24/0, H 49/0, N 5/0, S 2/0
Mass Tolerance : 1000ppm, 1mmu if m/z > 1
Unsaturation (U.S.) : -0.5 - 50.0

Observed m/z	Int%	Err [ppm / mmu]	U.S.	Composition
1 399.0610	100.00	-0.6 / -0.2	20.0	C21 H13 N5 S2

Figure S20. MALDI-TOF (top) and FAB+ high resolution (bottom) mass spectra of MTA.

Data : JMA95-EI001
Inlet : Direct

Date : 05-Jul-2018 15:59
Ion Mode : EI+

[Mass Spectrum]
Data : JMA95-EI001 Date : 05-Jul-2018 15:59
RT : 2.06 min Scan# : (26.29)
Elements : C 24/0, H 49/0, N 1/0, S 1/0
Mass Tolerance : 1000ppm, 1mmu if m/z > 1
Unsaturation (U.S.) : -0.5 - 30.0

Observed m/z	Int%	Err [ppm / mmu]	U.S. Composition
1 203.0763	100.00	-2.8 / -0.6	8.0 C12 H13 N S

Figure S21. Electron impact (EI+) standard (top) and high resolution (bottom) mass spectra of **4b**.

Bruker Daltonics flexAnalysis

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[Mass Spectrum]

Data : JMA103-EI001 Date : 25-Sep-2018 15:43

RT : 2.46 min Scan# : (105,171)

Elements : C 24/0, H 49/0, N 3/0, O 1/0, S 2/0

Mass Tolerance : 1000ppm, 1mmu if m/z > 1

Unsaturation (U.S.) : -0.5 - 30.0

Observed m/z	Int%	Err [ppm / mmu]	U.S. Composition
1 365.0651	100.00	-1.5 / -0.6	16.0 C19 H15 N3 O S2

Figure S22. MALDI-TOF (top) and FAB+ high resolution (bottom) mass spectra of **5b**.

[Mass Spectrum]
 Data : JMA108-EI001 Date : 24-Sep-2018 16:55
 RT : 2.63 min Scan# : (103,113)
 Elements : C 24/0, H 49/0, N 5/0, S 2/0
 Mass Tolerance : 1000ppm, 1mmu if m/z > 1
 Unsaturation (U.S.) : -0.5 - 30.0

Observed m/z	Int%	Err [ppm / mmu]	U.S. Composition
1 413.0763	100.00	-1.4 / -0.6	20.0 C22 H15 N5 S2

Figure S23. FAB+ high resolution (bottom) mass spectrum of Me-MTA.

5. Cyclic voltammetry

As displayed in Figure S23, except for **MPA** which shows the more positive oxidation peak potential at $E_{pa} = 0.60$ V, investigated molecules show one reversible oxidation peak. The presence of an additional methyl group in **Me-MPA** ($E_{pa} = 0.53$ V) leads to a negative shift of the oxidation peak compared to **MPA** in agreement with the electronic inductive +/ effect of the methyl group. A negative shift of 20 mV is also observed in the MTA-series. More importantly, replacing one phenyl ring by a thiophenic one in the MTA-series produces a more significant negative shift of the oxidation peak of 230 and 180 mV for **MTA** and **Me-MTA**, respectively. On the other hand, both structural changes weakly affect the first reduction peak. To summarize, CV analysis shows that both the introduction of a thiophene ring and a methyl group contribute to increase the energy level of the HOMO.

Figure S24. Cyclic voltammograms of the studied compounds, 1 mM in 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆/CH₂Cl₂ using Pt working and counter electrodes and a scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹.

Table S1. Electrochemical data of the donor compounds measured by cyclic voltammetry (0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ in CH₂Cl₂ and 100 mV s⁻¹ scan rate).

Compound	E_{pa} [V/Fc/Fc ⁺]	$E_{ox/onset}$ [V/Fc/Fc ⁺]	E_{pc} [V/Fc/Fc ⁺]	$E_{ox/onset}$ [V/Fc/Fc ⁺]	E_{HOMO} [eV] ^a	E_{LUMO} [eV] ^b	ΔE^{elec} [eV]
MPA	0.60	0.50	-1.23	-1.13	-5.30	-3.67	1.63
Me-MPA	0.53	0.41	-1.28	-1.16	-5.21	-3.64	1.57
MTA	0.37	0.26	-1.25	-1.14	-5.06	-3.66	1.40
Me-MTA	0.35	0.23	-1.27	-1.17	-5.03	-3.63	1.40

^a E_{HOMO} (eV) = $-(E_{ox}^{onset} + 4.8)$. ^b E_{LUMO} (eV) = $-(E_{red}^{onset} + 4.8)$.

6. Comparison of UV-Vis spectra of titled compounds in solution and as thin-films

Thin-films are prepared on ITO substrates by spin-coating chloroform solutions of each molecule and analyzed by UV-Vis spectroscopy (Figures S25-28). All thin-films show broader absorption bands than the ones observed in solution. However, two slightly different behaviors are observed. In the case of the MPA-series, the absorption maxima are 25-30 nm red-shifted compared to solutions whereas an opposite effect is observed, albeit less pronounced (6-8 nm), for compounds of the MTA-series. These results suggest different intermolecular interactions in the solid-state between **MPA** and **MTA** compounds.

Figure S25. UV-Vis spectra of **MPA** in CH_2Cl_2 and as thin-film deposited by spin-casting on ITO.

Figure S26. UV-Vis spectra of **Me-MPA** in CH_2Cl_2 and as thin-film deposited by spin-casting on ITO.

Figure S27. UV-Vis spectra of **MTA** in CH_2Cl_2 and as thin-film deposited by spin-casting on ITO.

Figure S28. UV-Vis spectra of **Me-MTA** in CH_2Cl_2 and as thin-film deposited by spin-casting on ITO.

7. Photoelectron Spectroscopy in Air (PESA) measurements.

Figure S29. PESA spectrum of **MPA** as thin-film deposited by spin-casting on ITO.

Figure S30. PESA spectrum of **Me-MPA** as thin-film deposited by spin-casting on ITO.

Figure S31. PESA spectrum of **MTA** as thin-film deposited by spin-casting on ITO.

Figure S32. PESA spectrum of **Me-MTA** as thin-film deposited by spin-casting on ITO.

Table S2. Optical data and frontier molecular orbitals energy levels determined by UV-Vis spectroscopy and PESA.

Compound	$\lambda_{\max}/\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ [nm]	ϵ [$\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$]	$\lambda_{\max}/\text{Film}$ [nm]	E_{HOMO} [eV] ^a
MPA	551	27000	582	-5.79
Me-MPA	559	41000	583	-5.70
MTA	657	30000	651	-5.58
Me-MTA	666	45400	658	-5.35

^a HOMO energy determined by PESA on thin-films.

8. Energy levels of frontier molecular orbitals

In order to draw an energetic diagram (Figure S32), estimation of the HOMO energy levels from PESA measurements is used, along with optical gaps shown in Table 3 in the main text. In good agreement with the CV data recorded in solution, the thiophenic MTA-derivatives exhibit higher HOMO levels and the *+I* inductive effect of the methyl groups in *para* positions, contributes also to a further energetic destabilization of the HOMO.

Figure S33. Energetic diagram for investigated compounds showing HOMO energies estimated from PESA. Values for C₆₀ are taken from reference ^[10].

9. Sensitive EQE_{PV} and EL measurements

EQE spectra measured with high sensitivity, as explained in main text, are used to evaluate the properties of the CT state. Fitting the spectra with Equation (5) allows determining the molecular parameters related to the CT state properties. Table S3 lists parameters derived from those fits.

Table S3. CT state parameters extracted from the fits to EQE_{PV} measurements.

Device, donor	E_{CT} [eV]	λ_{CT} [eV]	$f[(eV)^2]$
MPA	1.642	0.190	0.063
Me-MPA	1.621	0.257	0.105
MTA	1.435	0.214	0.079
Me-MTA	1.431	0.224	0.101

Non-radiative voltage losses can be also obtained directly from EL quantum yields (Equation (3) in the main text). The calculated values are summarized in Table S4 and it's worth pointing out that the trend in change of non-radiative losses follows the values obtained from the EQE_{PV} measurements.

Table S4. Electroluminescence quantum yields and corresponding non-radiative voltage losses.

Device, donor	EQE _{EL} [1]	ΔV_{nr} [V]
MPA	$9 \cdot 10^{-9}$	0.474
Me-MPA	$3 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.385
MTA	$4 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.436
Me-MTA	$4 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.377

10. Transient photovoltage

All measured TPV traces are fitted with a monoexponential decay function (Equation (S1)).

$$y = A \exp\left(-\frac{x}{t_0}\right) + y_0, \quad (S1)$$

where A is a constant, t_0 is the exponential time constant i.e., the time it takes for the signal to reach $1/e$ of its initial value and y_0 is a scaling parameter equal to the V_{oc} at given light intensity. The time constants are then plotted as a function of the V_{oc} and fitted with Equation (9), allowing to extract the lifetime of free charge carriers. The examples of fits to the TPV traces as well as extraction of the lifetime for devices based on **Me-MTA** molecule are shown in Figures S34 and S35 and the fitting parameters are summarized in Table S5.

Figure S34. TPV transients (gray lines) obtained for devices based on the **Me-MTA** molecule. Different values of V_{OC} are obtained by varying the illumination intensity of the bias light. Red lines represent fits to the data using a monoexponential decay function, as described in the text above.

Figure S35. Exponential decay time constants obtained from fitting the TPV traces are plotted as a function of V_{oc} (pink diamonds). The data is fitted with Equation (9) from the main text to obtain the recombination constant τ_0 (dashed line).

Table S5. Fitting parameters τ_0 and β extracted from TPV lifetime measurements.

Device, donor	τ_0 [μ s]	β [V^{-1}]
MPA	4.6	18.3
Me-MPA	79.5	19.6
MTA	131.7	27.5
Me-MTA	2763.7	28.7

Supporting References

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